

DEMONSTRATION OF A NOVEL LOW CONCENTRATION AND SOLAR CONTROL PHOTOVOLTAIC SYSTEM FOR BUILDING INTEGRATION

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ABSTRACT: PVSITES project has developed an ambitious set of BIPV solutions specially tailored to provide a comprehensive and robust answer to market demands. One of these solutions is a **low concentration PV solution with associated passive climate control properties for building integration in façades and skylights**. Glass-glass semitransparent PV modules in conjunction with integrated optical elements are proposed to concentrate solar radiation onto the cells during the central part of the year and allow light passing towards the interior of the building during the winter. At the central part of the year, the lenses deviate solar radiation onto the cells with a double effect: (1) an increase in PV production in comparison with a traditional PV system of same installed power and (2) a reduction in cooling demands due to an enhanced solar control, with less radiation entering the building during the summer. The savings provided by the system are obviously greatly enhanced in locations with high direct irradiation conditions. The system is being demonstrated in three experimental outdoor set-ups with different climates: two experimental test benches in ACCIONA facilities (Seville, Spain), Field Lab Testing facility at Tecnalia site (Derio, Spain) and FACT building at CEA-INES (Chambéry, France).

Keywords: Building Integrated PV (BIPV), Building Integration, Energy Performance, Environmental Effect

1 AIM AND APPROACH USED

Although space heating is still the dominant energy demand for buildings in most European countries, special attention should be paid to cooling, since the energy consumption it accounts for (mostly electric energy) is growing rapidly as a consequence of global warming. In this framework, a low concentration photovoltaic solution with associated passive climate control for building integration in façades and skylights is being demonstrated within H2020 PVSITES project (www.pvsites.eu). The system is composed by semitransparent glass-glass crystalline silicon PV modules in conjunction with integrated optical elements (Fresnel lenses). The optical system, with no mechanical parts, is designed to concentrate solar radiation onto the cells during the central part of the year and allow light passing towards the interior of the building during the winter.

An associated PV production enhancement and a reduction of the building cooling demand are expected during the spring-summer-autumn seasons. During this period, most part of the direct component of incoming solar radiation is redirected towards the solar cells, so that the PV modules behave as a low concentration system, providing a significant annual over generation for high and medium irradiation climates. At the same time, as there is a decrease in direct solar radiation within the building, greenhouse effect and its related building overheating are reduced. During the winter, diffuse radiation and most direct radiation reach the internal part of the building, not penalizing heating demands, and the

PV system produces under non-concentrated light, as a usual PV system would.

This technology has been previously demonstrated by Tecnalia in the greenhouses sector. PVSITES project introduces this technology into the building environment by demonstrating façade (shading elements) and skylight configurations.

The optical and electrical design has been performed by Tecnalia, by means of ray-tracing techniques and in-house developed algorithms for the Fresnel lens development. System optimization included the study of several parameters like lens width, Fresnel lens parameters, lens position, distance between lenses, solar cells position, weight of the different seasons balanced with latitude, cell occupancy and lens tilting. The glass-glass crystalline silicon BIPV modules were manufactured by Onyx Solar and the Fresnel lenses were manufactured by Film Optics.

The glass lenses have been tested under specific mechanical, ageing and fire reaction tests by Tecnalia and CTCV. The full system has been tested by INES under IEC 62108 standard for concentrated PV systems.

Figure 1: Mechanical test of the lens to ensure performance under wind load

In order to obtain accurate experimental results and relevant conclusions, prior to the mounting of the experimental setup, specifications concerning the design and installation of the integration structures, the definition of solutions to ensure the waterproofing of the test cells and the choice of suitable instrumentation. The monitoring in parallel of the BIPV skylight without Fresnel lenses as reference and of the low concentration BIPV skylight permits a full comparison of their performance.

A 6.7 m² BIPV skylight prototype has been installed on the flat roof of FACT experimental building at INES site, located in the Alps Valley. A one-year measurement campaign is performed in order to evaluate the impact of solar concentration on the thermal and electrical performance of the BIPV skylight as well as its influence on indoor thermal and visual comfort and energy consumption.

Two prototypes of BIPV system inclined at 20° and south-oriented were symmetrically integrated in skylight configuration above two similar test cells at the top floor of the FACT building using a wooden and aluminum integration structure. These components of 3.34m² are differentiated by the presence or not (reference) of Fresnel lenses ensuring a low solar concentration. They consist in 4 poly-Si glass-glass PV modules of nearly 30Wc connected in series and comprising 4 strings in parallel of 4 PV cells.

Since the total nominal power of the installed PV fields of nearly 120Wc is too low for the micro-inverters existing on the market, each system has been connected to a DC MPPT EL3000B electronic load ensuring a maximum power point tracking (MPPT).

For an accurate comparative analysis, the test cells walls have been insulated and their windows have been opacified in order to highlight the impact of the skylights on the indoor visual comfort. Also, rolling shutters have been installed for cold seasons in order to ensure waterproofing of test cells. The room temperature set points have been fixed at 21°C in winter and 26°C in summer.

A similar instrumentation has been installed on the two BIPV systems and tests cells in order to ease their comparison.

Figure 2: The two BIPV skylights configurations on FACT tool.

The integration of low-concentration shading elements for façade was accomplished at ACCIONA site, in Seville (Spain). Two PV glass curtain walls of 12.25 m² each were disposed in two testing cells with same configuration. One of them is being used as reference (no lenses) while the other integrates the lens system. They include a heating-cooling system whose set point have been fixed to 21°C. Both test cells monitor PV production, inner temperature and humidity and PV temperature. Besides, the POA and GHI radiation, outdoor temperature, outdoor humidity and wind are being monitored as well. A one-year experimental campaign is taking place.

Figure 3: ACCIONA test benches with the low concentration system in façade configuration

2 SCIENTIFIC INNOVATION AND RELEVANCE

The proposed BIPV solution will reinforce the catalogue of multifunctional BIPV solutions in the market, providing improved performance in terms of electricity generation and reduction of cooling demands, and glare mitigation, giving place to an unprecedented case in BIPV.

3 RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

Both at the INES and ACCIONA sites the test campaigns are performed with a 5 min time step during one year in order to obtain weather data, PV modules surface temperatures, electrical values, heating and cooling energy consumption data as well as thermal and visual comfort data. This will permit to validate the relevance of the BIPV system façade and skylight configurations in different climatic areas and to propose optimization solutions. Figure 4 (left) presents an example of electrical results obtained on the two BIPV façades on August 21th, including a comparison with previously simulated data. Figure 4 (right) shows the electrical power produced by the two BIPV skylight during a week in cold season (no concentration).

Figure 4 (top): Current produced by the two BIPV façades (with and without low-concentration) on August 21th. They are compared with simulated prediction (based on radiation received by the cells); (bottom): electrical power produced by the two BIPV skylight during a week in cold season.

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